

Schiff bases of toluidines : synthesis and effect of position of methyl group on biological potential

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Abstract : Condensation of 2-toluidine and 3-toluidine with benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes (1-8) resulted in the formation benzal-2-toluidines (1a-8a) and benzal-3-toluidines (1b-8b) respectively. The products were identified on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies and screened *in vitro* for their antifungal potential against three phytopathogenic fungi and two nematodes.

Keywords : Schiff base, toluidine, biological activity.

Schiff bases provide a potential site for both chemical and biological activity of compounds¹. The effect of presence of various substituents² in the phenyl ring of aromatic Schiff bases on the biological activity has already been reported. In continuation of work on the effect of position³ of substituent on the biological activity, this paper describes the synthesis of Schiff bases of 2-toluidine and 3-toluidine, their characterisation and their comparative evaluation for antifungal potential and nematocidal activity.

Results and discussion

Condensation of 2-toluidine with benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes in equimolar ratio resulted in the formation of crude solids (1a-8a) which were recrystallized from ethanol. The products have been identified and confirmed as benzal-2-toluidine (1a), 4-chlorobenzal-2-toluidine (2a), 4-hydroxybenzal-2-toluidine (3a), 4-methoxybenzal-2-toluidine (4a), 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-2-toluidine (5a), 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzal-2-toluidine (6a), 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzal-2-toluidine (7a) and 3-ethoxy-4-hydroxybenzal-2-toluidine (8a) respectively on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies.

In the IR spectra of these compounds the band at about 1630 cm⁻¹ is assigned to carbon-nitrogen double bond. The PMR spectra of the compounds in CDCl₃ indicate a one proton singlet at δ 8.4 due to azomethinic proton alongwith other characteristic peaks for the respective functional groups present in the molecule. For instance, the PMR spectrum of 3-ethoxy-4-hydroxybenzal-2-toluidine (8a) in CDCl₃ indicates a three proton singlet at δ

2.4 for methyl protons, a two proton quartet at δ 4.4 and a three proton triplet at δ 1.6 for ethoxy protons, a seven proton multiplet between δ 7.0 to 7.9 for aromatic protons and one proton singlet each at δ 8.4 and 8.9 for azomethinic and hydroxy proton respectively.

The products obtained by the reaction of 3-toluidine with benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes (1-8) in equimolar ratio after recrystallization from ethanol have been characterized as benzal-3-toluidine (1b), 4-chlorobenzal-3-toluidine (2b), 4-hydroxybenzal-3-toluidine (3b), 4-methoxybenzal-3-toluidine (4b), 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-3-toluidine (5b), 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzal-3-toluidine (6b), 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzal-3-toluidine (7b) and 3-ethoxy-4-hydroxybenzal-3-toluidine (8b) respectively on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies.

The IR spectra of these compounds contain a band at about 1620 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to >CH=N- linkage. In PMR spectra of the compounds in CDCl₃, all the protons have resonated in the expected field. For instance, the PMR spectrum of 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzal-3-toluidine (6b) in CDCl₃ indicates one proton singlet at δ 8.4 due to azomethinic proton, a three proton singlet at δ 2.5 due to methyl protons, a nine proton singlet at δ 3.9 due to methoxy protons and a six proton multiplet between δ 7.0 to 7.8 due to aromatic protons.

The Schiff bases of 2-toluidine (1a-8a) and 3-toluidine (1b-8b) have been screened *in vitro* for their antifungal potential against *Alternaria alternata*, *Helminthosporium gramineum* and *Myrothecium roridum* by spore germination inhibition method. Only seven of

the test compounds have ED₅₀ value less than 1000 ppm against *A. alternata* and the best among these is **8b** with ED₅₀ value of 160 ppm. Five of Schiff bases of 2-toluidine and three of 3-toluidine have ED₅₀ value less than 1000 ppm against *H. gramineum* and the best among these is **4a** with ED₅₀ value of 170 ppm. All the Schiff bases of 2-toluidine except **1a** and **2a** have ED₅₀ value less than 1000 ppm against *M. roridum* whereas only three Schiff bases of 3-toluidine have ED₅₀ value less than 1000 ppm against this fungus and the best among these is **8b** with ED₅₀ value of 160 ppm. In general the Schiff bases of 2-toluidine have been found to be more effective against *H. gramineum* and *M. roridum* whereas those of 3-toluidine against *A. alternata*.

The preliminary *in vitro* screening of the compounds **1a-8a** and **1b-8b** against *Ditylenchus myceliophagus* and *Caenorhabditis elegans* following the water screening technique⁴ at 2000 ppm indicated a variable amount of mortality. Only one of the compounds namely 4-methoxybenzal-2-toluidine (**4a**) has been found to cause mortality more than 60 per cent against both the test nematodes. Thus the compound **4a** possess better anti-fungal potential as well as nematocidal activity.

Experimental

All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis and the melting points are uncorrected.

Synthesis of Schiff bases of 2-toluidine : Benzaldehyde/substituted benzaldehyde (0.1 mol), 2-toluidine (0.1 mol) and methanol (100 ml) were taken in a beaker (250 ml). The mixture was warmed for a few minutes and allowed to stand at room temperature when crude solids separated out which were filtered and recrystallized from ethanol to get respective Schiff base with m.p. (°C) and % yield : **1a** (40, 60); **2a** (42,60); **3a** (183,81); **4a** (38, 62); **5a** (67, 90); **6a** (124, 92); **7a** (110, 75) and **8a** (142, 91).

Synthesis of Schiff bases of 3-toluidine : 3-Toluidine (0.1 mol) was taken in methanol (100 ml). To the above solution added benzaldehyde/substituted benzaldehyde (0.1

mol). The mixture was heated to get a clear solution. The clear solution was cooled when the crude solids separated out which were filtered and recrystallized to get respective Schiff base with m.p. (°C) and % yield : **1b** (41, 62); **2b** (190, 58); **3b** (50, 92); **4b** (68, 90); **5b** (70, 93); **6b** (75, 94); **7b** (80, 95) and **8b** (72, 94).

In vitro screening for antifungal potential : The stock solution of 2000 ppm of each compound was prepared by dissolving each chemical (20 mg) in absolute alcohol (0.5 ml) and the volume was made to 10 ml with sterilized distilled water. The required dilutions were subsequently made from the stock solution by adding sterilized distilled water. Small droplets (0.02 ml) of spore suspension in equal quantity with solution of the test compound were seeded in the cavities of cavity slides. These slides were placed in petriplates lined with moist filter paper. The petriplates containing cavity slides were incubated at 25 ± 1 °C for 20 h. The germination of spores was recorded and per cent spore germination inhibition was calculated and ED₅₀ values determined.

In vitro testing for nematocidal activity : About 100 nematodes of each genera were exposed to 2 ml solution of the test compound and observations for the number of living or dead nematodes were recorded after an interval of 96 h. The immobile nematodes with a definite posture were recorded as dead. After 96 h, the nematodes were transferred to distilled water and possible reversal of immobilized nematodes was recorded.

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